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The Effect of Agro ecological Practices in Soil Fertility and Nutrients Recycling with Beans-Rice Rotation

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Abstract

*this study examined the effect of residue management and crop varieties on soil fertility and nutrient recycling within the beans-rice cropping system. A split split plot experiment arranged in a Randomized Complete Block Design was used. Main factor was crop residues with three levels, sub factor was crop varieties of beans and rice with three levels and sub sub factor was four weed management practices. Soil samples were taken three times; before beans planting, after beans and rice harvest. The collected data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) at ($P < 0.001$). Results indicated a significant increase of pH, K and P after beans and a decrease after rice. OC and N were high in residues incorporated (RI) and lower in residues removed (RR), while pH, K and P were higher in residues burned (RB) and lower in RR. In beans tissue Potassium and Phosphorus were a higher in Wanja with interaction of RI and low in Uyole 96 and Mshindi with interaction of RB. Total nitrogen was significantly high in RI*M and low in RB*M at ($P < 0.001$). In rice plant tissue, potassium and phosphorus were highly significant at ($P < 0.001$) in RI with Faya variety while total nitrogen was significant high for Super Zambia (S.Z) in RR and lower in RB with Faya (F). It was concluded and recommended that beans-rice cropping practiced simultaneously with residues incorporation resulted in a significant increase of soil nutrients, ensured available nutrients for plant uptake and hence to be advocated and adopted by farmers.*

Keywords: Agroecology, Crop rotation, residues management, nutrients recycling

1. Introduction

Continuous cultivation of rice with monocropping does contribute to the serious depression of soil nutrients, organic matter in rice fields and reduction of crop productivity due to improper management of fertilizers, tillage and crop residues (Singh and Singh, 2001). Crop residues are materials or remain left in the field after the crop has been harvested, including part of crop plants like stalks, stems, leaves and seed pods (Uddin et al., 2016). Once crop residues are left in the field perform a critical role in nutrient recycling to improve soil productivity. Recycling of crop residues has great potential to return significant volume of plant nutrients to the soil (Fatema et al., 2016). Apart from nutrient addition, the incorporation of crop residues in the field

also maintains the soil's physical and chemical properties and increases the general ecological balance of the crop production system (Krishna et al., 2004). The common crop residual management choices that exists among farmers are burning, incorporation, removal of the straw from soil surface, retention and mulching (Krishna et al., 2004).

A study by Krishna et al. (2004) revealed that burning crop residues completely to facilitate timely planting causes environmental pollution, large losses (up to 80%) of N, 25% of P and 21% of K and 4-60% of S. Such practices results into significant killing off beneficial soil insects and microorganisms. The distribution of crop residues on the field surface helps to protect the fertile surface soil against erosion but has an effect on machinery failures and affects seed sowing (Uddin et al., 2016). Crop residues management help farmers earn more income with a reduced amount of labor, fertilizer and irrigation but still has a great challenge to manage crop residues effectively and efficiently to enhance crop production (Tanvir et al., 2013). The rice straw and roots once are incorporated into the soil after harvest; as they decay, these plant parts release bound nutrients that become available for uptake by the succeeding crop (Schueneman and Rainbolt, 2008).

Practicing crop rotations in rice fields is the predominant approach to overcoming the negative aspects of short cropping sequences and monocultures in intensive cropping systems (Grzebisz et al., 2018). In irrigated lowland, rice is planted only one season per year due to restrictions on water use permits and water shortage; hence land use can be improved by using the post-rice wet period to grow-legume crops. Legumes are appropriate rotational crops with rice since they can mature early in 3 months, are drought-tolerant, capable of nitrogen fixation into the soil, and can be grown as post-rice crops using the receding and residual soil moisture (Zhu et al., 2016). However, these crops generally result into changes in soil fertility, owing to the incorporation of crop residues and N fixation from the atmosphere (Zhang et al., 2017; Ockerby et al., 1999). Limited studies have been done on residual management in rice fields towards improving crop yield but were restricted into one crop and continuous cropping system. A work done by Dao et al. (2019) revealed the relationship between crop-residue management practices and nutrient flows in the soil-plant system in monocropping rice fields but designate different crop residues management techniques in rice-beans rotation. In this study, soil and plant nutrients were analyzed in relation to different crop residue management practices in rice beans crop rotation for determination of nutrient recycling within the cropping system.

2. Method

2.1 Location of the Study area

The experiment was carried out at Makwale irrigation scheme at Kyela district located in the Southern part of Mbeya Region with latitude 9037' south, and longitude 33052' east with mean annual rainfall ranging from 2000mm and 3000mm and mean daily temperature of 23°C.

2.2 Experimental set up

Split split plot experiment laid down in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications, each having three main plots and three subplots and four sub sub plot (Gomez and Gomez, 1984). The size of the main plot was 8 m × 11 m, sub plot was 11 m × 2 m and sub sub plot was 2 m × 2 m. Main plot treatments were crop residues management namely removed (RR), residues incorporated (RI) and residues burned (RB). Treatment in sub plot were three crop varieties; rice were SARO 5(S), Faya (F) and Super Zambia (SZ) and common beans were; Uyole 96 (U), Wanja (W) and Mshindi (M). Residues were first chopped and distributed uniformly in the plot, incorporated in the soil during field preparation and left for decomposition under moist conditions for 21 days. Treatments in sub sub plot were four weed

management regimes (control, mechanical weeding twice, pre emergence only and pre emergence combined with mechanical weeding) The sub sub plots were formed by soil bunds harrowed by hand hoe, leveled for beans sowing and rice transplanting. In residues removed treatment, crops after harvest were cut near the ground surface and taken out from the field while residues were burnt, after crop harvest, residues were cut near the soil surface, distributed uniformly and left drying for 14 days, burned, and the plots were tilled, leveled for sowing and transplanting. Beans were planted at a spacing of 20 cm by 50 cm, and two seeds were placed per planting hill. Rice seedlings were transplanted at the age of 28 days after sowing with a spacing of 20 cm by 20 cm in 10 rows; each had 10 holes of plants and two seedlings were placed per hole.

2.3 Soil sample collection

Determination of nutrients recycling in the soil, a soil tube auger was used to collect the soil samples by subjecting it into the soil at a depth of 40 cm, considering root zone depth. In each main plot of 56 m², samples were collected four times in diagonal and mixed well to obtain a composite sample of 0.5 kg. A clean cloth of 2 m² was used in mixing thoroughly the soil before sub-sampling. The soil was spread evenly and divided into 4 quarters. The two opposite quarters were rejected, and the rest were mixed again. The process was repeated till the remaining amount was half a kilogram as a composite sample, the soil was collected, put in a clean cloth bag, and each bag was properly marked for sample identification. Three samples per replication were obtained based on the treatments (residues removed, burned and incorporated) making a total number of 9 composite samples for the whole experiment. Chemical analysis was done for determination of soil pH, Organic carbon (OC), (Nitrogen (N), Potassium (K) and Phosphorus (K) as described by (ICARDA, 2001)

2.4 Plant sample collection

The rice plant samples were collected at maximum tiller formation near panicle initiation, while for beans were collected near flowering. The tillers were sampled at the center of the plot at an average of 5 tillers per plot, cut above the ground. Plant samples were placed in paper bags, labeled and carried to the laboratory. In the laboratory, the samples were dried in the oven at a temperature of 70°C for 72 hours until a constant dry weight was obtained. The samples were cut into small pieces, grinded in a mill, poured into the glass bottles with tight stoppers and a polyethylene bag, and finally stored in a cool and dark place. Then the samples were taken further for chemical analysis for determination of plant tissue analysis of N, K and P as per (ISRIC, 2002) manual.

3. Results

3.1 Soil nutrient cycling under bean-rice rotation with different residue and weed management practices

Results revealed significant differences ($P < 0.05$) with beans-rice rotation and three residues handling practices in all analyzed soil nutrients. There were significant interactions ($P < 0.05$) between rotation and residual handling were observed in OC, TN, and P (Table 3.1)

Table 1: Summary of significance level of nutrients

Treatment	df	pH	OC	TN	P	K
Beans-Rice cycle (B-R)	2	**	**	**	**	**
Residue Handling (H)	2	**	**	**	**	**
B-R*H	4	ns	**	**	**	ns

Note: R*H- Interaction effect, ** stands for significance at 5 %, and “ns” stands for not-significance, OC stands for organic carbon, TN stands for total nitrogen.

3.2 Soil pH

Results in table 2 below show that there were very highly significant increases of pH at ($P < 0.001$) from 5.58 before experimental setup (Baseline) to 5.84 after bean cropping season and slight decrease in the second season (rice season), from 5.84 to 5.55.

Table 2: Potassium, soil pH, Total Nitrogen, Organic Carbon and Phosphorus

TWR	SP	OC (%)	TN (%)	EK Cmol+/kg)	AP (mg/kg)
Baseline	5.58 b	1.222 c	0.157 c	0.2259 a	7.469 a
Post-Bean	5.84 a	1.004 b	0.0474 b	0.1999 a	6.372 b
Post-Rice	5.55 b	0.851 a	0.0093 a	0.1519 b	6.25 b
P-value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Cv	5.1	33.2	27.2	10.2	28.7
L.S.D	0.0774	0.0911	0.00682	0.02769	0.515

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P < 0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: PV = P-value, CV = Coefficient of Variability, and LSD = Least Significant Differences, TWR=Time within Rotation, SP=Soil pH, available P contents are based on Bry-1 extraction method, EK-Exch. K, AP=Available P, TN=Total Nitrogen, OC=Organic carbon, TWR=Time within rotation

3.3 Soil organic carbon content

There was very high significant influence of bean-rice cultivation cycle on soil organic carbon (OC) content at ($P < 0.001$) as shown in Table 2. Generally, there was a significant decrease in average soil organic carbon contents in the first season (bean growing season), where the OC decreased from 1.22 % at the onset of the experiment to 1.004 % after the bean harvest. Moreover, the OC further decreased from 1.004 % to 0.851 % in the second season (rice growing season). However, the average values (pooled means) did not consider the effect of either residue handling practice or weed management regimes or interactions with them, in which the effect was evaluated herein.

3.4 Soil total nitrogen (TN) %

The results of plots' average soil total nitrogen (TN) contents at different collection time points within a bean-rice rotation are indicated in Table 2. Compared to the baseline (at the onset of an experiment), TN contents decreased very high significantly from 0.157 % to 0.0474 % after the first season (bean growing season) and ultimately to 0.0093 % after the second season (rice growing season) at ($P < 0.001$).

3.5 Soil potassium (Cmol+/kg)

The exchangeable potassium contents of the soils at different time points within bean-rice rotation are shown in Table 2. Generally, there was very high significant increase in soil exchangeable K content from 0.151 Cmol+/kg at the onset of the experiment (baseline) to 0.225 Cmol+/kg after the first season (bean growing season) and then a slight decrement to 0.199 Cmol+/kg after the second season (rice growing season) at $P < 0.001$.

3.6 Available soil phosphorus (P) (mg/kg)

The amount of soil available P was observed to increase very high significantly at ($P < 0.001$) from 6.372 (mg/kg) at the onset of an experiment to 7.469 (mg/kg) after the first cycle (bean

growing cycle) and then decreased to 6.25 (mg/kg) after the second season (rice growing cycle) as indicated in Table 2

3.7 Soil pH in different residue handling practice

Results revealed that burning of crop residues were resulted to very high significant increment of soil pH (5.852), as compared to either RI or RR ($P < 0.001$). (Table 3)

Table 3: Potassium, Total Nitrogen, Soil pH and Phosphorus in different crop residue handling practices

RHM	SP	ATNC (%)	EK mol+/kg)	AP (mg/kg)
RB	5.852 a	0.0614 a	0.2187 a	7.381 a
RI	5.61 b	0.09305 b	0.1858 ab	6.779 a
RR	5.516 c	0.05921 a	0.1732 b	5.932 b
P-value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Cv	5.1	27.2	10.2	28.7
L.S.D	0.0774	0.01342	0.02769	0.515

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P < 0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: RB = Residue burning, RI = Residue Incorporation, RR = Residue removal, PV = P-value, CV = Coefficient of Variability, and LSD = Least Significant Differences, RHM-Residue Handling Method, SP=Soil pH, ATNC=Average Total Nitrogen Content, EK=Exch. K, AP=Available, values presented are means of three replications; available P contents are based on Bry-1 extraction method.

3.8 Soil total nitrogen in different crop residue handling practice

Incorporation of crop residues (RI) resulted in a very high significantly (0.09305%) at ($P < 0.001$) soil total nitrogen contents than RR or RB (additive effect of bean and rice residues considered) Table 3

3.9 Soil potassium in different crop residue handling practice

Residue handling practices had significant effect on soil exchangeable K content Table 3. The potassium content of the soils varied significantly with varying residue handling methods ($P < 0.001$), where the highest soil K was recorded in plots with RB, followed by the plots with RI and then the lowest being the plots with RR.

3.10 Available Phosphorus in different crop residue handling practice

Residues management practices resulted to very high significantly influence in soil available phosphorus contents, as indicated in Table 3. Generally, RB resulted in significantly higher P contents (7.381 mg/Kg) followed by RI 6.779 mg/Kg compared to RR 5.932 mg/Kg, at ($P < 0.001$).

3.11 Soil potassium (K) (Cmol/kg) in different crop residue handling practice

The potassium contents in bean plants varied very high significantly ($P < 0.001$) between the treatments (previous rice residue management practice). The plots with the RI or RB had plants with higher K contents (0.2589 Cmol/Kg or 0.2489 Cmol/Kg) respectively than the plots of RR (Table 4).

Table 4: Potassium, Total Nitrogen and Phosphorus contents in rice residues management

Crop residues	K (Cmol/kg)	Total N %	P(Mg/Kg)
RR	0.1878a	0.3267a	5.429a
RB	0.2489b	0.3622ab	8.388b
RI	0.2589b	0.3711b	9.813b
PV	<0.001	<0.015	<0.001
CV	13.4	8.8	26.3
LSD	0.03004	0.03149	2.315

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P=0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: RB = Residue burning, RI = Residue Incorporation, RR = Residue removal, PV = P-value, CV = Coefficient of Variability, and LSD = Least Significant Differences, K=Potassium, N= Nitrogen, P= Phosphorus, values presented are means of three replications.

3.12 Total Nitrogen % in rice tissue within residues management

The results on previous crop residues' effect on plant Nitrogen (N) concentration in beans crop tissue are presented in table 4. RR prior planting of bean plants resulted in significantly higher N content of bean plants (0.371 %), followed by RI 0.3622% ($P < .015$). The plants grown in plots with RB had the lowest N content (0.32 %).

3.13 Phosphorus contents in rice tissue within residues management

Results on the effect of crop residues on Phosphorus (P) content in bean plants were very highly significant at $P < 0.001$ in residues incorporated by 9.813% between the treatments, as shown in Table 4.

3.14 Potassium contents in bean plants tissue among beans varieties

The results of potassium uptake abilities of three bean varieties (table 5) revealed significant differences in K contents of bean plants between the treatments (varieties) at ($P < 0.001$). Two varieties (W and M) accumulated high amount of potassium 0.2633 and 0.2344 respectively compared to the U bean variety.

Table 5: Potassium and Total nitrogen within beans varieties

Beans varieties	K (Cmol/kg)	Total N%
Uyole 96	0.1978a	0.3311a
Mshindi	0.2344b	0.36b
Wanja	0.2633b	0.3689b
PV	<0.001	0.05
CV	13.4	8.8
LSD	0.03004	0.03149

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P=0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: PV = P-value, CV = Coefficient of Variability, and LSD = Least Significant Differences, K=Potassium, N= Nitrogen, P= Phosphorus, values presented are means of three replications.

3.15 Total nitrogen (%) concentration within bean varieties

There was significant differences in nitrogen content among the beans varieties where M had a high Nitrogen content of (0.3689%), followed by the W variety of 0.36%, while U had a lower nitrogen content of (0.3311%) at $P = 0.05$, as indicated in Table 5.

3.16 Potassium content within bean varieties

The interaction effect between bean varieties and previous residue management practice on plant potassium contents was assessed and found statistically very high significant at ($P < 0.001$), as indicated in figure 1. Wanja variety was observed to accumulate more K when the previous season's residues were either burnt or incorporated compared to when residue was removed.

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P = 0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: RR= Residues removed, RI= Residues Incorporated, RB= Residues burnt, M=Mshindi, W=Wanja, U= Uyole

Figure 1: Interaction effect of beans varieties and crop residues managements on plant's N and K contents of bean leaf.

3.17 Interaction effects between rice residue management and bean variety on plants tissue' total nitrogen content

The interaction effects between rice residue management method and bean variety on plants' total nitrogen content in the subsequent season. Accordingly, the interaction effect was significant ($p < 0.003$) in Fig. 1.

3.18 Interaction effect of rice residues management practices and bean varieties on phosphorus contents in bean plants tissue

The result showed high significant difference $P < 0.002$ in Phosphorus content among the beans varieties in interaction with crop residues management, where the highest was on W*RI at 11.77 Mg/Kg, followed by RR*M had 11.337 Mg/Kg, while the lowest value was in M*RR 3.81 Mg/Kg (Fig 2).

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P=0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: RR= Residues removed, RI= Residues Incorporated, RB= Residues burnt, M= Mshindi, W=Wanja, U= Uyole

Figure 2: Interaction effect of beans varieties and crop residues managements on plant's P contents of bean leaf

3.19 Rice nutrients recycling within rice beans cropping system

Treatments combinations or interaction of crop residues and rice variety resulted in significantly high Nitrogen content in rice plants by 5.29 % for SZ variety in residues removed plots, and the lowest was 0.19% for F variety plant in the residues incorporated plots at $P < 0.001$ as indicated in Fig 3. Regardless of residue handling practices, the SZ variety was observed to have higher N contents. However, unlike the two other varieties, they incorporation of residues resulted in lower N content for the F rice variety.

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at P=0.001 according to Tukey’s (HSD) test

Key: RR= Residues removed, RI= Residues Incorporated, RB= Residues burnt, S= SARO 5, F=Faya, SZ= Super Zambia

Figure 3: Plant analysis results for three varieties of rice plants grown under three different crop residues management in Total N%

3.20 Interaction effect of beans residues management and rice varieties on rice Potassium (K) (Cmol/kg)

There was very high significant difference among crop residues management interacting with rice varieties in rice plant Potassium content where SZ planted in residues incorporated plot had a high content of Potassium by 2.927 Cmol/kg, and the lowest was S 1.323 Cmol/kg in residues removed at P<0.001 among interaction of crop residues and rice varieties Fig 4. For instance, uptake of Potassium by F variety was significantly higher when residues were incorporated as compared to either burnt or removed residues.

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at P=0.001 according to Tukey’s (HSD) test

Key: RR= Residues removed, RI= Residues Incorporated, RB= Residues burnt, S= SARO 5, F=Faya, SZ= Super Zambia .

Figure 4: Plant analysis results for three varieties of rice plants grown under three different crop residues management in Total N (%) and K (%)

3.21 Nitrogen contents rice plant tissue in beans residues management practices

Three residue management practices (incorporation, removal, and burning) were evaluated for their effect on rice N contents of subsequent rice plants. The results are presented in Table 6, indicating very high significant differences between the treatments at $P < 0.001$. Plots with removed residues had plants with the highest N contents (1.94 %), followed by the plots with incorporated residues (1.148 %). Residue burning results in plants with the lowest N contents (0.487 %). The observed trend is similar to N contents in bean plants grown on the same plots in the previous season.

Table 6: Potassium, total nitrogen and phosphorus contents in rice residues management

Crop residues	Total N %	P(Mg/kg)	K (Cmol/kg)
RB	0.487a	7.002a	1.798a
RI	1.148b	12.563b	2.278b
RR	1.94c	8.813a	1.696a
PV	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
CV	15.4	16.5	2.7
LSD	0.183	2.657	0.213

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P=0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: RB = Residue burning, RI = Residue Incorporation, RR = Residue removal, PV = P-value, CV = Coefficient of Variability, and LSD = Least Significant Differences, K=Potassium, N= Nitrogen, P= Phosphorus, mean values with different lower case letters are statistically significant different at $P<0.05$.

3.22 P contents in rice plant tissue in beans residue management practice

Results on the effect of crop residue management practices on the Phosphorus (P) content of rice plants are shown in Table 6. The residue handling practice had a significant effect on rice P contents ($P < 0.001$), whereby residue incorporation resulted in higher P (12.563 Mg/kg) followed by residue removal (8.813 mg/kg). Burning of bean residues resulted in the lowest P content (7.002 Mg/kg) of rice plants in the next season. Generally, the trend for P contents in rice plants across residue handling methods is in accordance with the P contents in bean plants grown on the same experimental plots in a preceding season.

3.23 K (Cmol/kg) contents of rice plants tissue in beans residue management practice

Also, results in Table 6 indicate the significant difference in Potassium content in rice plants among the management of the residues where rice plants in residues incorporated had high potassium 2.278 Cmol/kg at $P < 0.001$.

3.24 Total N (%) contents in rice plants tissue within varieties

This study also evaluated the nitrogen uptake ability of three rice varieties (F, S, and SZ) when grown on a bean-rice rotation system. The results are presented in Table 7, and there were significant differences

between treatments at ($P < 0.001$), whereby SZ variety had the highest plant N contents compared to either F or S varieties.

Table 7: Potassium, phosphorus and total nitrogen contents within rice varieties on

Rice varieties	Total N %	P(Mg/kg)	K (Cmol/kg)
F	0.236a	7.538a	2.228b
S	0.29a	7.723a	1.52a
SZ	3.049b	13.118b	2.023b
PV	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
CV	15.4	16.5	2.7
LSD	0.183	2.657	0.213

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P=0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: S = SARO 5, F = Faya, S.Z = Super Zambia, PV = P-value, CV = Coefficient of Variability, and LSD = Least Significant Differences, K=Potassium, N= Nitrogen, P= Phosphorus, mean values with different lower case letters are statistically significant different at $P < 0.05$.

This study further investigated the P uptake abilities of rice varieties as presented in Table 7, and there were very high significant differences in the three varieties' P uptake abilities varieties ($P < 0.001$). The SZ variety had the highest P content (13.118 Mg/kg), followed by S (7.723 Mg/kg) and F variety (7.538 Mg/kg) which are statistically comparable. Among the varieties, there were also highly significant differences among the rice varieties: F had high Potassium content 2.228 Cmol/kg, and S had the lowest value by 1.52 Cmol/kg at $P < 0.001$. Unlike Nitrogen and Phosphorus, the uptake of Potassium by F varieties is higher compared to that of SZ variety of S.

4. Discussion

4.1 Soil pH

Increase of soil pH in season two of rice crop might be attributed by work of rice roots which produces huge amount of organic acids and reduces the soil pH. This finding is related to Hoffland et al. (2006), who reported that the reduction of soil pH in a rice-growing season is attributed to the fact that the roots of rice plants can exude large quantities of Low Molecular Weight Organic Acids (LMWOA) that lowers soil pH. Production of LMWOA is among physiological adaptive mechanisms used by the rice plants to obtain nutrients such as Phosphorus and zinc (Adeleke et al., 2017). Another reason for the observed decrease in soil pH during the rice growing season is probably the leaching of exchangeable bases due to higher soil water contents. During the study, the plots were more inundated during the rice than during the bean growing season, where similar results in a legume-maize rotation by number of studies (Garrity and Shoals, 1992; Rakotoson et al., 2022; Uzoh et al., 2019). Also increase of soil pH in burned residues plots might be due to the ashes effect of RB, which is alkaline in nature. These results are in line with previously study by Chungu et al. (2020). Principally, residue burning leads to the accumulation of ashes, which has a liming effect on soil (Gummert et al., 2020). Moreover, burning residues limit microbial activities in the soil, including organic matter (OM) decomposition and for that reason, lowers the production of organic acids associated with OM decomposition (Jamali et al., 2021).

4.2 Soil and plant nitrogen (TN) content within bean and rice varieties, crop residues, and crop rotation

The decrement in soils' total nitrogen content is probably due to the nutrient mining effect of the crops (Sutton et al., 2013) as there was no externally supplied nitrogen. However, high total nitrogen content at the onset of the experiment is attributed to the utilization of exceedingly higher doses of inorganic nitrogenous fertilizers as reported by farmers in the study area. Moreover, despite this negative trend of total N content (average), the effect of residue handling practice was examined herein. Moreover, increment of N in incorporated residues is probably due to the mineralization of organic nitrogen contained in the residues to inorganic nitrogen forms through activities of heterotrophic soil microorganisms. Similar results have been reported by Takahashi et al. (2003), Ye et al. (2014); Weil and Brady, 2017 and Gummert et al. (2020) that residues incorporation (RI) was observed to increase soil total nitrogen over time. On the other hand, when the residues are removed from the field, all the nutrients (including N) taken up by the plants are also removed along (nutrient mining) and therefore leading to nutrient depletion from the soil in the long run (Jamali et al., 2021). Again, the burning of crop residues has been reported in the literature that it loose up to 80 % of the Nitrogen to the atmosphere, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions (Robertson and Groffman, 2006).

The difference in nitrogen content in residues management also can be explained by the fact that combustion of residues results in volatilization loss of about 98 to 100 % nitrogen previously bound to organic compounds contained in the residue. According to (Gelderman, 2009 and Jamali et al., 2021), residue burning not only results in low N availability for plant uptake but also implies to environmental concern since it emits a significant amount of the main air pollutants such as N₂O CO₂, and CH₄. Moreover, a relatively lower plant N contents for beans grown on plots with incorporated residue may be due to the unpromising quality of rice straws; - wider carbon to nitrogen ratio (C: N) of rice straw has been reported to result in net immobilization and therefore loss of significant quantities of nitrogen from the soil (Wang, 2001; Takahashi et al., 2003; Gummert et al., 2020). Takahashi et al. (2003) reported in their investigation that the short-term effect of rice straw incorporation on N uptake is minimal compared to its long-term effect. Also the lower N contents in rice crop for the rice plants grown in plots with burnt residues are probably due to the effect of combustion on soil nitrogen (about 98 to 100 % of N is lost to the atmosphere) (Gelderman, 2009).

Incorporation of bean residues was expected to have increased N uptake by rice plants compared to where residues were removed since residues of leguminous plants are associated with net-mineralization of N (legumes have a narrow C: N ratio) (Meena et al., 2018). The most probable reasons for these unprecedented results likely due to narrow C: N ratio of bean plant residues resulted in rapid decomposition and consequent mineralization of N, most of which is exposed to losses before plant uptake (Takahashi et al., 2003). Therefore, there was a lack of synchronization between N mineralization from the residues and the uptake by rice plants in the successive season (Sandhu et al., 2022). According to Myers et al. (1994) and Masunga et al. (2016), the synchrony between nutrient mineralization and uptake by plants can be achieved through proper planning for the time of residue incorporation and residues with a wider C: N ratio has to be applied at least two months before planting while the materials with narrow C: N ratio are to be incorporated just prior planting (Takahashi et al., 2003.) With reference to bean varieties on total nitrogen content the differences in might be due to the ability of plants to take up nitrogen from the soils and their use-efficiency been highly attributable to the interaction between plants' genotypes and environmental factors. However, the observed differences can be attributed only to variation in varieties' genetic character because treatment randomization is believed to have controlled the environmental factors (Mead et al., 1993). Also, the study by Katarzyna et al. (2020) reported that the differences in nitrogen absorption and accumulation among

cultivars growing under the same environmental conditions are influenced by genetic effects or physiological limitations.

In rice varieties, low soil nitrogen in Faya variety treated in incorporated crop residues might be contributed by genetic and physiological processes of the plant in nitrogen accumulation and utilization as well as the decomposition process of the residues. This is revealed by a study done by Maya et al. (2013), who found that a substantial genotypic variation in N uptake ability under different soil moisture conditions existed among diverse rice genetic resources in which cultivars revealed greater N uptake in a wide range of soil characteristic and conditions. These findings substantiated that the N uptake and assimilation in the plant organs does not only influenced by available N in the soil but also by genetic characteristics. Moreover, rice crop was planted after beans harvest and some its residues were incorporated in the soil, burned and others removed. Beans plants, apart from N being able to fix nitrogen but also have high N contents as a result of the decomposition process and limit N availability for plant uptake. This is supported by the work done by Baoqing et al. (2015), who reported that if the nitrogen from plant residues is greater than the N demand of the microbial population during plant residue decomposition, the mineralization process becomes dominant and makes limited available N for plant uptake. In rice also the variation of total N plant contents is described by the fact that higher nitrogen uptake by plants is not necessary assurance of higher yield performance by the crop if the N-use efficiency of the crop is substandard. McDonald & Standing (2003). However, nitrogen is essential in rice plants since it improves crop yield performance through its effect on vegetative development plant biomass, and crop yield. Nitrogen fertilization has also been reported to enhance rice tillering and panicle development (Hussain et al., 2022).

4.3 Soil and plant Potassium content in varieties, crop residues, crop rotation

The reduced amount of soil K content after the rice growing season can be physiologically explained by the fact that rice plants accumulate a lot of potassium, leading to K-mining from soils (Andrews et al., 2021). Furthermore, since rice season was associated with the inundation of soils, the rate of nutrients leaching (especially exchangeable bases like K) also was high. Therefore, it is highly recommended not to continuously cultivate rice plants on the same land (rice mono-cropping) as it may lead to depletion of soil K. Also with respect to crop residue handling practices the immediate positive effects of residues burned (RB) on soil potassium contents might be due to ashes produced which are rich in potassium content. The findings are in agreement with previously report in the literature by (Saha et al., 2009 and Zhang et al., 2021 that firing residues leaves behind ashes that are rich in potassium and other basic nutrients of the like (Gummert et al., 2020). However, in the long term basis, burning of rice residues has been reported to reduce soil K content since it lowers soil organic carbon content and subsequently cation exchange capacity (CEC) and, in turn, leaching of basic cations (Zhang et al., 2021). Based on plant analysis, crop residues management on beans potassium contents of subsequent bean plants the variation of potassium could be attributed to the ability of the beans plant in K uptake and accumulation in plant organs. These findings are online with Gummert et al. (2020), who reported that rice plants accumulate up to eighty percent (80 %) of its potassium content in straws, and therefore, rice is regarded as among the crops with K-rich residues (Andrews et al., 2021); secondly, Potassium in plant tissues is freely mobile (not tightly bound to biomolecules), thus allowing it to be easily released to the surrounding moist environment by osmolality (Marschner and Marschner, 2012). Thirdly, unlike nitrogen, potassium remains in the ash when the residues get burnt. For this reason, RI and RB resulted in higher soil K content and its subsequent uptake by bean plants grown in the proceeding season. The tallying results have been reported in the literature (Saha et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2021). In rice potassium content, the influence of residue management practice can be ascribed to the

fact that legume incorporation has a positive effect on soil potassium contents; - it increases K content by up to 45.78% (Gautam et al., 2021). Moreover, incorporating leguminous crops is known to increase organic matter, reducing leaching losses of cationic nutrients in soils (Coppens et al., 2006). The lower K content of plants grown in plots with removed residues might be attributed to the nutrient mining effect because all of the Potassium contained in residues is being taken out of the field (Jat et al., 2020). Unlike removal, residue burning had a minimal negative effect on plant K content since residue combustion causes a loss of only 25% of Potassium and the rest is retained in ash (Heard et al., 2006).

In addition to that, bean varieties had an effect on potassium contents of bean plants as the three bean varieties differ significantly in genetic traits, particularly in nutrient uptake and accumulation in the plant organs. According to Fageria et al. (2011), the potassium uptake ability of bean varieties is a genetically controlled trait, although environmental factors such as soil water and nutrient availability may have a significant influence. Therefore, W, and M had higher K uptake abilities among three varieties, and U had the lowest. Wanja variety was observed to accumulate more K when the previous season's residues were either burnt or incorporated compared to when residue was removed. This variety was observed to have higher uptake of K, and thus its K requirement was probably higher than either Mshindi or Uyole. Therefore, management practices such as residue incorporation are required for the varieties with higher K requirements to increase K contents in the soils. Furthermore the different of rice varieties in potassium (K) rice plant content might be due to the fact that uptake of potassium by SZ and S varieties were independent of the method used to manage crop residues in the preceding season. This is supported by Suremi et al. (2005), who reported that the incorporation of residues that are rich in K content expressively increased the total K uptake due to its restful consumption by the crops. Thus, the incorporation of crop residues in the soil increases the availability of K in soil and subsequent uptake by the plant.

4.4 The effect of bean-rice varieties, crop residues, crop rotation on soil and plant Phosphorus content

Low amount of in nutrients after rice harvest might be attributed to nutrient mining in the grown crops since there was no externally applied P source, and rice plants have higher phosphorus requirements for growth and development. Therefore, it is essential to consider the application of ecologically friendly P sources such as rock phosphates to avoid soil phosphorus mining in the long run (Szilas et al., 2007). In comparison with crop residue handling practice on soil available Phosphorus is that, incorporated of crop residues (RI) does increase soil nutrients after decomposition and this become a reason to phosphorus increase in incorporated plots. We hereby describe the observed disparities to the additive effect of P mineralization from the incorporated rice residue prior to the first season and bean residues prior to the second season (Meena et al., 2018). RI has been reported to increase soil nutrient availability, including Phosphorus, both in the short term and in the long term (Ye et al., 2014; Coulibaly et al. (2020). The effect of rice residue management practice on soil phosphorus contents of might be due to the fact that burning crop residues do reduces phosphorus availability and uptake by the crop plant grown in a successive season. This can be ascribed to the fact that combustion of crop residues results in a loss of about 20 % P from soils (Jamali et al., 2021). Furthermore, residue burning suppresses soil microbial activities such as Arbuscular, Mycorrhizae and phosphate solubilizing microbes, which play a major role in enhancing the bioavailability of P for plant uptake (Khan et al., 2014; Gummert et al., 2020; Jamali et al., 2021). According to Gautam et al. (2021), the composited rice straws or rice-legume residues were reportedly more efficient for increasing soil P availability. However, similar to the findings in this study, rice straws alone can enhance soil P availability and uptake by the plants as per (Gautam et al., 2021).

Generally, the trend for P contents in rice plants across residue handling methods is in accordance with the P contents in bean plants grown on the same experimental plots in a preceding season. Therefore, we can ascribe this to the additive effect of the incorporated rice residue prior to the first season, and bean residues prior to the second season. Reports by Meena et al., 2018, Ye et al. (2014), Coulibaly et al. (2020), and Zhang et al. (2018) have underlined a significant contribution of crop residue incorporation on availability of essential nutrients, including P, in a long term. Similar to findings of this study, Guautam et al. (2021) also reported an additive effect of successive incorporation of rice straw and legumes on increasing available phosphorus contents on the soil and its consequent uptake by plants. Phosphorus in plants plays essential roles such as structural development of biomolecules (Nucleic acids, DNA and RNA), root development, and particularly in rice, several yield components such as panicle number, grain weight and seed-setting rate (Tian et al., 2017). However, despite the observed differences in varieties P uptake, probably due to genetic disparities, the use-efficiency of these varieties also determine crop grain yield. Unlike Nitrogen and Phosphorus, the uptake of Potassium by F varieties was higher compared to that of SZ variety of S. Therefore, from this observation, it can be noted that SZ variety has higher mining abilities for N, Nitrogen and Phosphorus. The observed variation in the K uptake ability of varieties is attributed to their genetic disparities. When taken up in rice plants, K performs several indispensable roles, such as maintaining cellular osmolality, facilitating photosynthetic and metabolites translocation, enhancing nitrogen-use efficiency, and eventually contributing to both grain yield and quality (grain processing and cooking quality) (Marschner and Marschner, 2012; Atapattue et al., 2018).

4.5 Interaction effects between rice residue management method and bean variety on plants' total nitrogen

The interaction effects indicating that varieties' ability to take up nitrogen from the soil depends on which method was used to handle rice straws in the previous season. For example, if the residues are incorporated, decomposition depends on the means of the incorporation, like chopped or not before incorporation. The work done by Anja et al. (2015) stipulate that residue decomposition was significantly faster in fields with rice straw incorporated into the soil compared to rice straw scattered on the field surface. Again, the variety with higher N uptake/requirement (M variety) accumulated shallow N when residues are burnt. In contrast U variety with the lowest N uptake was observed to accumulate more N when residues were burnt than either residues incorporation or removal. Low N uptake in incorporated residues might be contributed to the low rate of decomposition on rice straw and finally releasing N for plant uptake. Chao et al. (2019) and Nakajima et al. (2016) reported incorporation of rice straw in the soil undergoes a long and complex decomposition process via the activities of decomposers by breaking down of organic matter and regulated by the chemical composition and moisture of the rice straw and temperature. These findings are online also with the study done by Yijiao et al. (2022), who reported that the burning of plants/residues does increase N recovery in bulk roots during the summer warming period and hence increases the potential N uptake by the plants. Also, the study by Azza et al. (2007) revealed that lower N uptake by the plant in the incorporated rice residue plots was attributed to relatively high C/N ratios; hence the incorporation of rice residue at a suitable time is vital for exploiting the valuable effects of rice residue incorporation. Generally, the early incorporation of residues in the soil influences the immobilization process in the early stages, and the consequent slow remineralization permits the plant to utilize N more efficiently.

4.6 Interaction effect of rice residues management practices and bean varieties on phosphorus contents

Incorporation of residues has a greater influence on phosphorus availability in the soil and, ultimately, its

uptake by beans plant. The results similar to Cycl et al. (2006), who reported that higher P uptake by plants with the incorporation of residues is due to more synchronization in P released from the organics or decomposing residues, the root exudates and organic molecules released during the decomposition of organics solubilize the P precipitated as sparingly soluble compounds finally increase P uptake by the plant.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has generally indicated that, beans - rice interchange cultivation impacts on variation of soil nutrients such as total nitrogen, potassium and available phosphorus where the decrease was after rice harvesting. Moreover incorporation of crop residues resulted to high plant and soil nutrients content compared to residues removed and burnt in both rice and beans seasons. In Plant analysis, Uyole 96 variety of beans and Super Zambia for rice had high plant nutrients content once treated in plots with residues incorporated. Thus, long-term incorporation of crop residues together with beans–rice cultivation will enhance soil nutrients increase and ultimately decrease the external supplement of synthetic fertilizer. Hence it is recommended that in the study area, farmers to start cultivating beans with Uyole 96 variety after rice harvest from July and rice with SARO 5 variety from December. The introduced beans season apart from the advantages of improving soil fertility but also will offer income and become another source of food nutritional to farmers as it is a new crop in the study area.

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